

MOBILE COMMUNICATION SYSTEMS AND THEIR BASIC REQUIREMENTS

Gafurov A.Sh.

TUIT named after Muhammad al-Khwarizmi

Assistant of the Department of Technology of mobile communication

E-mail: gafurovasror686@gmail.com

Annotation: This article presents the basic requirements of a modern mobile communication system, namely the requirements for high load balancing, scalability and mobile device management in a mobile communication system.

Key words: Mobile communication, basic requirements, high capacity load balancing, mobile device management.

The Era of technology has revolutionized communication with the introduction of mobile and wireless communication. Mobile communication system may be defined as a communication system that allows people to communicate without utilizing any physical link, disregarding, location, time, and distance. The idea of wireless communication was set forth by Marconi in 1885 with the invention of Wireless Telegraph.

Mobile Communication is the use of technology that allows us to communicate with others in different locations without the use of any physical connection (wires or cables). Mobile communication makes our life easier, and it saves time and effort.

A mobile phone (also called mobile cellular network, cell phone or hand phone) is an example of mobile communication (wireless communication). It is an electric device used for full duplex two-way radio telecommunication over a cellular network of base stations known as cell site.

The following are the features of mobile communication:

High capacity load balancing: Each wired or wireless infrastructure must incorporate high capacity load balancing.

High capacity load balancing means, when one access point is overloaded, the system will actively shift users from one access point to another depending on the capacity which is available.

Scalability: The growth in popularity of new wireless devices continuously increasing day by day. The wireless networks have the ability to start small if necessary, but expand in terms of coverage and capacity as needed - without having to overhaul or build an entirely new network.

Figure 1. Scalability

Network management system: Now a day, wireless networks are much more complex and may consist of hundreds or even thousands of access points, firewalls, switches, managed power and various other components.

The wireless networks have a smarter way of managing the entire network from a centralized point.

Figure 2. Network management system

Role based access control: Role based access control (RBAC) allows you to assign roles based on what, who, where, when and how a user or device is trying to access your network.

Once the end user or role of the devices is defined, access control policies or rules can be enforced.

Indoor as well as outdoor coverage options: It is important that your wireless system has the capability of adding indoor coverage as well as outdoor coverage.

Figure 3. Mobile device management

Network access control: Network access control can also be called as mobile device registration. It is essential to have a secure registration.

Network access control (NAC) controls the role of the user and enforces policies. NAC can allow your users to register themselves to the network. It is a helpful feature that enhances the user experience.

Mobile device management: Suppose, many mobile devices are accessing your wireless network; now think about the thousands of applications are running on those mobile devices.

Mobile device management can provide control of how you will manage access to programs and applications. Even you can remotely wipe the device if it is lost or stolen.

Roaming: You don't need to worry about dropped connections, slower speeds or any disruption in service as you move throughout your office or even from building to building wireless needs to be mobile first.

Roaming allows your end-users to successfully move from one access point to another without ever noticing a dip in a performance.

For example, allowing a student to check their mail as they walk from one class to the next.

Redundancy: The level or amount of redundancy your wireless system requires depends on your specific environment and needs.

For example: A hospital environment will need a higher level of redundancy than a coffee shop. However, at the end of the day, they both need to have a backup plan in place.

In conclusion, wireless communications globally are something that people can expect as technology advances. Wireless communications have a lot of benefits and can make the world a lot more efficient. It does have concerns though as with every other new advancement that is made in today's world. The issues with security regarding access to a person's personal information or the negative impact that it may seem to have on society are a few things that are holding back the progress that wireless technology could be making. Also, not all population of the world do not have mobile broadband access. With more research and experiments conducted, the problems associated with wireless communications can be reduced and make it a more significant part of the world. Wireless technology will be very important in the near future where the need for wires connecting individual devices seems to be coming to an end.

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